

1 Acquired hearing loss in zebrafish: the effects of aging and noise on gene
2 expression and auditory function on the inner ear saccule

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26 Abstract

27 Exposure to increasing noise levels is known to cause attenuation of hearing acuity,
28 resulting in temporary and/or permanent threshold shifts. Aside from noise, ageing is
29 another major factor that induces sensorineural impairment. However, the interaction
30 between noise-induced hearing loss (NIHL) and age-related hearing loss (ARHL) as
31 well as their underlying molecular control mechanisms are not fully understood.

32 In this study, we investigated NIHL and ARHL and their interaction in the zebrafish
33 model. Furthermore, we analysed changes in gene expression in the saccular epithelia
34 in the same experimental groups.

35 The hearing sensitivity was determined based on Auditory Evoked Potential recording
36 technique in both young control (YC, 7-8 months old) and old fish (OC, 19-21 months
37 old), as well as in both young and old fish after 150 dB re 1 μ Pa 24h white noise
38 treatment (YN and ON, respectively).

39 Aged zebrafish showed up to 15 dB shift in the auditory thresholds. While noise
40 treatment also induced threshold shifts, these were up to 23 dB and 10 dB in young and
41 old specimens, respectively. Transcriptomic analyses of the saccular epithelia revealed
42 1,192 (540 up- and 652 down-regulated), 108 (29 up- and 79 down-regulated) and 1,111
43 (490 up- and 621 down-regulated) genes differentially expressed in YN, OC and ON
44 groups compared to young control (YC). Both ARHL and NIHL showed differently
45 expressed genes associated with Extracellular matrix (ECM)-receptor interaction
46 pathways, which are known to play key roles as guidance molecules, establishing
47 connections and forming synapses between pre- and postsynaptic cells.

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